

PHILOLOGY

EFFECT OF FAMILY NEGLECT ON THE GENERAL WELL-BEING OF THE AGED IN EGOR LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, EDO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Elderly neglect is a problem that has been linked to deteriorating social values, economic recession, and rapid rise in migration, all of which have harmed family structures, which in turn has negatively influenced the values of respect and care for the elderly. This study investigates the effect of family neglect on the health of the aged in Egor L.G.A. A total of 400 respondents of elderly men and women were chosen randomly from each of the ten political wards that make up the Egor local government area. For this project, the subject under inquiry was explained using the principles of learning theory. Data from the respondents in the field was gathered via questionnaires and in-depth interviews. Twenty respondents participated in an in-depth interview, while 400 received questionnaires. The responses from both groups were used to explain the data collected in the field. Findings show that the majority of the respondents about 23.7% said they had only been neglected occasionally by their family caregiver while 29% of respondents who are the majority, said they had developed more than one health problem as a result of family neglect. Families should consider providing for the basic needs of the elderly as part of their everyday responsibilities. Doing so will help reduce senior neglect and enhance the quality of life for the elderly.

Keywords: Effects, Elderly, Family, Well-being, Neglect.

Introduction

Elder neglect has now become more widely recognized as a concern for social workers, sociologists, and public health professionals globally. Elderly neglect is anticipated to worsen as the world's senior populations grow, particularly in low-income countries. According to a retrospective analysis by Cooper, Selwood, and Livingston (2008), the prevalence of EAN in developing countries ranged from 13.5 percent to 28.8 percent, while the prevalence in developed countries ranged from 3.2 percent to 27.5 percent as we speak. Because of this, the WHO (2018) argued that by the time the population of those over 60 years old reaches 2 billion in 2050, 32 million older people will have suffered from neglect in one way or another. When an aged person's necessary physical, social, security, and healthcare needs are not met, this is known as neglect (Mudiare, 2013). According to Bonnie & Wallace (2002) neglect occurs when a family caretaker willfully or unwillfully fails to provide for the fundamental requirements of the elderly, which include nutrition, shelter, dress, healthcare, etc. Regrettably, the public is unaware of the growing prevalence of this problem. The cause of elderly neglect by family caregivers in Nigeria was attributed to changing socioeconomic structure, migration, marriage, unemployment, and the failure of the government to include the elderly in national social welfare benefits (Ajomale, 2014). The elderly people's well-being may be severely impacted by family caregivers' neglect. For example, the Inattention to the elderly, makes them more vulnerable to emotional stressors like abuse, loneliness, despair, and anxiety, all of which can lead to prolonged psychological strain which may cause physical illness or even death (Dong, 2005; Dong et al, 2009). However, in Nigeria, Akwe Ibom

state the prevalence of elderly neglect is 46.7% while that of Ekiti state was found to be 60.9% (Olayinka, 2007). The victims (the elderly) continue to endure in silence and suffer in pains that are connected with the scourge which in turn affects their total well-being (Ajomale, 2014).

Statement of problem

Concern over the universal aging and neglect problem has grown recently, whether in rural areas, metropolitan areas, or more developed or less developed nations around the world (Sijuwade, 2017). Some of the factors contributing to the rise in elderly caregiver neglect include increasing urbanization, migration, economic difficulty, poverty, etc., which have an impact on family structures. The traditional social values and network of intergenerational exchange in Africa have gradually been drained due to the rapidly changing socio-economic structures (Cohen & Menken, 2006; Ajomale, 2014). Due to the fast-shifting socio-economic systems, traditional social values and their system of intergenerational interaction have been drastically reduced in Africa (Cohen & Menken, 2006; Ajomale, 2014). Even though the elderly contribute greatly to their families, communities, and governments, they frequently receive inadequate care, a poor benefits package, and are neglected (Help Age International, 2008). Today the elderly face social discrimination due to their age in both formal and informal organizations, and the civilization they helped create is now excluding/neglecting them. (Abdulraheem & Parakoyi, 2005); The elderly's health is severely impacted (psychologically, emotionally, socially trauma) by this negligence. Because senior neglect could have a severe impact on our society shortly, there is an urgent need for awareness of the issue.

Neglect of the Elderly in the Family

This is one form of abuse elderly people face today in our society and it is the refusal or failure of an individual or family to fulfill their obligation to their elderly which could either be intentional or unintentional (Ajimale, 2014). The withdrawal of attention by the younger family members toward the elderly, failure to provide for the elderly the right nutrition, the inability to give them (aged) good medical health care, refusal by the family caregiver to also manage the physical, and emotional needs of elderly can create a gap which is called neglect (Olayinka, 2007). Family neglect of the elderly can occur when there is no adequate care given to the elderly by the family or withholding affection and a general lack of interest in the older person's social and psychological well-being and it includes the failure to assist with the activities of daily living and personal hygiene of the elderly (Ajomale, 2007).

The research study by Fajemilehin, Ayandiran & Salami (2007) revealed that some young adults and family members are faulty in the area of neglecting their elderly parent or loved one. This can be attributed to the changing social system and the failing economy in the country which had created a high rate of unemployment and increased poverty rate; making it difficult for a family to cope in the area of providing all the needs and care their elderly parents or loved one may need (Mudiare 2013). Ogboru, (2007) said that some people who had aging parents who are dependent on them complained that they do not have enough to even take care of their immediate needs in the family such as house rent, children's school fees, food, etc, how then could they provide all they need for their aged parents when they are still struggling to reach their own needs and this has led to the increased level of abandonment of the elderly. Fajemilehin et al, (2007) in the past aged people were hardly seen in the stress of working around without a home to stay, looking and, begging for money and food to eat because they had been abandoned by their children or loved ones who were taboo in the past in Nigeria/Africa and where the family fails to care for their aged parents the community assist but today the community is silent about this issue. Olayinka (2007) argued that it is so today because of the breakdown of the family system which had become weak due to increasing unemployment, high poverty rate, high rate of migration from rural to urban and to other foreign lands, etc. After many of these created the gap that led to this social disorder of elderly neglect or vulnerable aged people as we can weakness in our society today. Today our state capitals in Nigeria are places where you find elderly street beggars who were abandoned by their families and a majority of them have children and loved ones who have failed in their responsibilities to protect them making them victims of neglect and if nothing is done now by the families and constituted authorities to checkmate this growing challenge we might weakness as a social problem that will be difficult to control in the nearest future. Regardless of the socio-economic difficulties families should do everything possible to provide emotional, social, and monetary help for the elderly because how well the elderly can deal

with changes in their health, income, social engagements, and other areas as they age greatly depends on the support they receive from their family members (Kaur, Kaur, and Venkateshan, 2015). For example, the bulk of elderly people in India still reside with their immediate families, and they are cared for mostly by them (Tanuja, 2012).

The Effect of Elderly Neglect

The Psychological Effect of Neglect on the Elderly

This is referred to as emotional maltreatment; it includes the deliberate infliction of psychological torture or isolation in the elderly person (Dong, Simon & Gorbein, 2007). The neglect of the elderly can cause fear, pain, loss of appetite, sickness, and social isolation. All this makes the elderly person feel dehumanized and in turn, he or she may develop mental illness. Some studies have reported the high amount of abuse older people experience from depressive symptoms and psychological distress (Dong, Simon & Gorbein, 2007; Dyer, Pavlik, Murphy & Hyman, 2002). These include feelings of guilt, shame, loneliness, loss of self-esteem, embarrassment, fear, anxiety reactions, helplessness, insecurity, and post-traumatic stress syndrome (Daichman, 2001; Cisler, Begle, Amstadter & Acierno, 2012) Dong, Simon & Gorbein, 2007).

Physical Effect

The elderly may be unable to defend themselves because they usually have less physical strength. Studies have also revealed that elderly people who are subjected to neglect are more prone to physical injuries (Lachs, Williams, O'Brien, Pillemer & Charlson 2008; Anetzberger, 2004). Injuries may result in deleterious and life-altering situations such as hip fractures, chronic pain, need for support, disability, and a move to assisted living or ultimately premature death. Neglect has been associated with increased incidence of malnutrition, dehydration, hypothermia, hyperthermia, and pressure sores, which further complicates the health issues of the elderly (Lachs, Williams, O'Brien, Pillemer & Charlson (2008). Neglect, therefore, is the withdrawal of proper attention and deliberate refusal to render assistance or support in reaching the social, medical, psychological, and material needs of the elderly person. (Olayinka, 2007). As a result of these, some elderly people hurt themselves through self-isolation, starving themselves, expressing grief (regret), etc. They do all this just to seek attention from their loved ones who refuse to give them support or the adequate attention they need (Olayinka, 2007).

Social Impact

Elderly neglect or elderly abuse has a significant impact on the individual, family, and society because it affects social functioning. The compromise in health may necessitate increased help from family and community services (Fajemilehin, Ayandiran, & Salami, 2007). It may result in having fewer contacts with family members, violent actions, and withdrawal from social circles (Anetzberger, 2004).

Social Exchange Theory

Social exchange theory argues that two people must agree to be involved in an exchange of value and both parties must positively evaluate if the two people will evenly profit from the association. The theory also

stresses that the exchange between two people involves giving and taking that should be balanced because if one party gives more than the other if not properly managed there might be a breakup in the relationship. Based on the explanation of this theory elderly neglect may occur where the aged person is dependent on the caregiver without any contribution from the elderly the caregiver may be overwhelmed if not financially buoyant or in a situation where the caregiver has a lot of responsibilities to take care of like children school fee, rent, electricity bills, etc. this may lead to the failure for the caregiver to adequately provide the needs of the elderly or can even lead to the abandonment of the elderly. So, therefore, it is believed by this theory that elderly neglect is due to the over-dependence of the aged on the caregiver. As a person gets older, they turn out to be weaker in strength, and defenseless, and, some of them become more reliant on their children/relatives/friends for support or help, which might boost the risk of them being neglected. According to Bowling (2007) if a caregiver feels he/she is overstressed/stretched by the over-reliance of the elderly it may lead to detest which in turn can lead to abusive action from the caregiver-like neglect of the elderly (Bowling, 2007). For example, in a situation where the caregiver expects to get a reward from other family members for supporting that person if the caregiver does not get the reward neglect may occur. According to Periet et al, (2009) stress that old people who are financially buoyant may hardly experience neglect from caregivers but may well be susceptible to financial extortion. While Avalon (2011) said those elderly who are poor face the threat of neglect. In other words, due to the imbalance in the relationship of both parties (between the elderly and caregiver) the abuse of social expectations concerning independence gives birth to a

perpetrator who tries to re-establish some kind of control through intimidation or neglect (Boudreau, 2003; Ritter & Lampkin, 2011).

Methodology

This investigation aims to investigate the impact of elder neglect on families in the Egor local government district in Benin City, Edo State. The local government region is divided into ten (10) political wards, each of which is home to more than 45 communities. According to the 2006 census, the Egor local government district has a total population of 339,899, including 16,890 seniors who are 60 years of age or older. Using Taro Yamane's formula, the sample size was determined. Elderly men and women who are at least sixty (60) years old made up the sample of 400 participants who were randomly chosen from among the ten wards that comprise the local government of Egor. With the help of a structured and semi-structured questionnaire, the study used both qualitative and quantitative techniques of data gathering. The structured questionnaire was split into two parts: Section A deals with socio-demographic information, and Section B deals with questions that address the study's goal. Using a purposive sample technique, the questionnaires were distributed to 231 elderly men and 169 elderly women, and 15 respondents participated in in-depth interviews. The instrument's internal consistency reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha (α). The final figure revealed a coefficient of 0.75. While in-depth interviews were transcribed using basic descriptive and narrative methods, structured questionnaire data was analyzed using percentages and frequency distribution using SPSS version 20. Both quantitative and qualitative analyses were used to examine the survey data. Tables are used to display the outcome.

4.1 Table

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

	Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Male	231	57.8
	Female	169	42.3
	Total	400	100
Age of Respondents	60-69years	211	52.7
	70-79years	141	35.3
	80+	48	12
	Total	400	100
Marital Status	Single	12	2.8
	Married	269	63.8
	Separated	41	13.7
	Widowed/Widower	83	19.7
	Divorced	17	4.0
	Total	422	100
Religion	Christianity	256	64.0
	Muslim	76	19.0
	Traditional	41	10.0
	Other	29	7.0
	Total	400	100
Level of Education	No Formal Education	73	18.3
	Primary	94	23.5
	Secondary	150	37.5
	Tertiary	83	20.8
	Total	400	100

Source: fieldwork Feb-March, 2021

The aforementioned table shows that the majority of respondents, 57.7 percent are men, while the proportion of women is 42.3%. Additionally, the table shows that the majority of respondents 52.7% are between the ages of 60 and 69; 53.3% are between the ages of 70 and 79; and 12.0% are between the ages of 80 years. The table also reveals that 63.8 percent of respondents are married, 19.7 percent are widows or widowers, 13.7% are separated, 2.8% are single, and 4.0

percent are divorced. The aforementioned table also shows that of the 400 respondents, 256 (64%) are Christians, 76 (19%) are Muslims, 41 (10.0%) are African traditional worshipers, and 29 (6.7%) are members of other religions. The chart also shows that 73 respondents (17.3%) have no formal education, 94 (23.5%) have a primary school diploma, 150 (37.5%) have a secondary school diploma, and 83 (20.8%) have a certificate from a tertiary institution.

4.2 Table

Health Implication of Family Neglect on the Elderly in Egor L.G.A

	Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Frequency of neglect?	Only once	139	34.7
	More than once	122	30.5
	Few times	95	23.7
	Always	31	7.8
	Undecided	13	3.3
	Total	400	100
As an aged person which of these health challenges have you experienced as a result of family neglect?	Sleeping problem	83	20.7
	Depressive symptom's	57	14.3
	Stress and Anxiety	52	13.0
	Sickness of Loneliness	82	20.5
	I have experienced more than one of these health issues	116	29
	Undecided	10	2.5
	Total	400	100
As an aged person which of these Physical impacts have you experienced as a result of neglect?	Malnutrition	69	17.3
	Dehydration	37	9.3
	Physical Injuries	53	13.3
	I have experienced more than one of these physical impacts	115	28.7
	Undecided	126	31.5
	Total	400	100
Which of these Social challenges have you faced as a result of family neglect?	Fewer contact with family	118	29.5
	Withdrawal from social circles	103	25.8
	Total neglect by family caregivers I have experienced both	61	15.3
	I have experienced more than one of these.	108	27
	Undecided	10	2.5
	Total	400	100

Source: fieldwork Feb-March, 2021

According to the data in the table above, 34.7% of respondents stated they had experienced neglect just once, 30.5% said they had been neglected more than once, 23.7% said they had only been neglected occasionally, 7.7% said they had always been neglected, and 3.3% were unsure. The table also revealed that 29% of respondents who are the majority, said they had experienced more than one of these health problems as a result of family neglect. Additionally, 20.7 percent of participants said they had developed sleeping problems as a result of caregiver neglect, 14.3% said they had depressive symptoms, 13 percent said they had stress and anxiety, and 2.2 percent of respondents said they were unsure. According to the table's results, 17.3 percent of respondents said they were physically malnourished, 9.3 percent had experienced dehydration, and 13.3 percent had suffered physical injuries. However, 28.7 percent of respondents said they had experienced more than one physical effect as a result of neglect, and 31.5 percent were unsure. Finally, the table showed that about 29.5 percent of the participants, who make up the

majority, admitted they had fewer contacts with family, 25.8 percent of the respondents said they were experiencing withdrawal from social circles as a result of their age, while 15.3 percent agreed they were experiencing total neglect from family, 27 percent said they had experienced more than one social ostracism as a result of their age, and 2.5 percent were undecided.

As regards social exclusion experienced by the respondents due to family neglect?

One of the respondents who is 72 years of age said:

My family members do not call me often even my children call me once or twice a week they just left me with my grandson who is in senior secondary school. (IDI 13-04-2021)

Another respondent who is 82 years of age said:

I rarely attend church or social events because I cannot afford to hire a driver. When I ask my children to accompany me to a social event, they often offer me excuses or make occasional promises, but they never

show up as a result of their busy schedules, which is upsetting. (IDI 5-5-2021)

In furtherance to the above another respondent said:

My son, you barely ever see individuals helping to support attendance at events outside the home. Every time I ask my kids to take me out, they always give me an excuse that makes them feel disrespected, but whenever they get changed, they still come. (IDI 15-04-2021)

As regards the impact of family neglect on the health of the elderly?

One of the respondents a 76 years old woman said:

I fell in the bathroom and hurt my right leg because I can't see clearly at night. If I asked anyone in the home to help me right away, they would be upset because I was disturbing their sleep. So, what shall I do? I must assist myself. (IDI 18-04-2021)

In addition, the respondent also said:

I'm constantly concerned because I can't go to the places I'd love to see, and because of how my family, friends, and relatives occasionally treat me—and to make matters worse, these are people whose lives I've positively impacted in one way or another—I sometimes have sleepless nights. If I don't call, they won't call to say hello or to check on me. is that great? (IDI 18-04-2021)

Another respondent said:

Remember, my son, that loneliness, anxiety, and fear are natural parts of aging. Because I am an old man and this is what I am going through, I am speaking from experience when I say this. (IDI 16-04-2021)

He further added:

For instance, you may be concerned about not knowing how your children and grandchildren are doing because they are far from you. When I contact them to check in on them, they may excuse themselves by saying they are busy and even when they return my call, they may do so at an odd hour. So occasionally, all of this makes me anxious. (IDI 16-04-2021)

This can also be linked to the statement by Lachs et al (2008) who said that over 31, 118 cases of elderly neglect has been associated with increased incidence of malnutrition, dehydration, hypothermia, hyperthermia, pressure sores, which further complicates the health issues of the elderly.

Discussion of the Results

The study's results are discussed in this subparagraph in light of its goals. According to the results of the questionnaire, the majority of those who participated in the interviews (57.8% of them were aged males). According to the study, the majority of respondents (52.7% percent) are between the ages of 60 and 69; 63.8% percent of them are married; and the respondents are overwhelmingly Christians while most of the respondents have education qualifications.

The analysis shows that the majority of respondents had either experienced neglect once or more than once at the time this research was conducted, which raises the question of how family neglect affects the health of the elderly in Egor L.G.A. According to the results, the majority of elderly respondents had at least one health condition, with sleeping problems accounting for 20.7% of cases, depressive symptoms

for 14.3%, stress and anxiety for 13%, and loneliness as a disease for 20.5%. While 29% admitted they had experienced more than one of the listed conditions. The results show that 13.3% of respondents said they had bodily injuries as a result of family neglect (such as falling in the bathroom, etc.), while the majority of participants stated that they experience social exclusion as a result of family neglect. These results support (Help Age International's, 2008, statement that said elderly people also experience societal execution which is due to their age, because of their age their primary functions/ responsibilities within the informal and formal sectors are reduced or taken away from them.

Conclusion

If family caregivers do not provide the required care for the elderly in our culture, the issue of elder neglect cannot be adequately addressed. Society must foster a culture where aging is seen as a normal stage of life, in which anti-aging attitudes are not encouraged, where older people have the privilege to live in homes free of neglect, and where they have the opportunity to fully engage in social activities. To improve the quality of life for the elderly and to lessen the problem of aged neglect in the family, families should consider caring for the aged as part of their routine obligation to meet this group's basic needs. The government should also establish policies that will protect the interests of the elderly.

Recommendations

(1) Families should consider taking care of the elderly as part of their routine duty to meet this group's fundamental needs, which would assist decrease senior neglect and improve the elderly's quality of life.

(2) There is an urgent need for society to increase public knowledge of the importance of elder care, which will in turn help inform people about the need for better attitudes toward the elderly and prevent elder neglect.

(3) Elderly parents should receive the best care possible from their families. This will help lessen their levels of anxiety, sadness, loneliness, disease, etc., which will make the aged less stressed as a result, help them live longer and with greater happiness.

(4) All levels of government should enact legislation to safeguard the rights of the elderly in our society.

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